

Voluntary Disclosures and Financial Reporting Quality of Quoted Commercial Banks in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of voluntary disclosures on the financial reporting quality of Nigerian commercial banks, focusing on earnings persistence as a proxy for reporting quality. Nigerian banks are important to the nation's financial stability, and transparency in their reporting is essential for fostering stakeholder trust and informed decision-making. Amid global financial scandals and rising demand for corporate accountability, voluntary disclosures have gained attention as a means to mitigate information asymmetry and improve transparency. However, inadequate voluntary disclosures in Nigerian banks may hinder stakeholders, including investors and regulators, from making informed assessments, thereby affecting reporting quality. The study investigated the influence of voluntary disclosures, specifically capital adequacy ratio (CAR), return on assets (ROA), net interest margin (NIM), and earnings per share (EPS), on earnings persistence in the sector. Ex-post facto research design was used. Data from 20 commercial banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group over a six-year period were also obtained. The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression statistical technique was used to evaluate the relationship between these variables. The result of the analysis revealed that CAR and ROA significantly influenced earnings persistence, with CAR showing a positive effect (coefficient = 0.0290, $p = 0.020$) and ROA also showing a positive effect (coefficient = 0.1506, $p = 0.014$). In contrast, NIM had a negative significant effect, and EPS was not significant. The results revealed a positive correlation between

voluntary disclosures and improved financial reporting quality, as evidenced by more stable and persistent earnings. The study concluded that enhanced voluntary disclosures foster greater transparency, which can increase investors' confidence and improve the regulatory landscape. These findings suggest that encouraging voluntary disclosures could play a pivotal role in strengthening Nigeria's banking sector, with implications for regulatory frameworks, investors' decisions, and overall market efficiency. The study recommended that enhancing transparency in CAR disclosures and focusing on improving ROA reporting could boost earnings stability.

Keywords: voluntary disclosures, earnings persistence, financial reporting quality, capital adequacy ratio (CAR), return on assets (ROA)

Introduction

Voluntary disclosure involves providing information beyond what is required by Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) and the Securities and Exchange Commission's rules, offering insights into a company's financial health, risk management, and corporate governance. It includes strategic information on products, competition, customers, financial information (such as earnings forecasts and stock prices), and non-financial information (environmental, social, governance, and sustainability performance). Voluntary disclosures are crucial for stakeholders, helping them make informed investment decisions by clarifying the financial and non-financial exposures and contingencies a company might face. They also reduce information asymmetry and enhance transparency in capital markets.

The adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) has increased disclosure requirements, raising the quality and relevance of disclosed information. This trend is significant in the banking sector, where stakeholders heavily rely on financial information for decision-making. Understanding the impact of voluntary disclosures such as corporate social responsibility, capital allowance ratio, and others on financial reporting quality is crucial for stakeholders to assess the transparency and accountability of Nigerian commercial banks. This increased focus on voluntary disclosures reflects the evolving regulatory landscape and the importance of transparency in the banking sector. Mandatory disclosures are the minimum information required by law, while voluntary disclosures provide additional valuable insights. The stakeholder's perception often leans towards the

undue advantage of managers who may selectively disclose information, leading to information asymmetry and potential negative consequences.

Despite the importance of voluntary disclosures, there is limited research on their impact on the financial reporting quality of Nigerian commercial banks. This study addressed this gap by examining the relationship between voluntary disclosures and financial reporting quality over a six-year period, focusing on measures such as Earnings Persistence (EP), Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Earnings Per Share (EPS), Net Income Margin (NIM), and Return on Assets (ROA). By shedding light on these dynamics, the study aims to provide valuable insights for regulators, policymakers, and other stakeholders in the Nigerian banking sector, contributing to the existing body of knowledge, policy decisions, and corporate practices.

Statement of the Problem

Globally, voluntary disclosures have been a controversial issue, and the level of compliance is still uncertain even when the yearning for financial information disclosure is increasingly needed by every stakeholder. For the benefits of the business environment, organizations are required to disclose the least levels of information, known as mandatory disclosures. Therefore, practically most organizations go along completely with those least levels of the mandatory disclosure even though it is neither sufficient nor appropriate to meet users' needs for corporate information. This increases the need for additional information requirements. This additional information is known as voluntary disclosure. The separation of ownership and management of companies creates what are known as information asymmetries. Annual reports are usually used to reduce the information gap between the management and the investors. However, the financial statements do not provide sufficient information to users, which increases the information gap between information providers (managers) and information users (stakeholders and others). In addition, the current demands for information are greater and more diverse than in the past. This highlights the need for a wider range of information compared to what was previously sufficient. Thus, to reduce this problem, firms need to disclose more information voluntarily (Adeniyi & Olugbenga, 2019).

Recent decades have witnessed financial scandals that led to the collapse of long-standing companies. Extreme lapses in financial reporting quality have given rise to high-profile scandals that resulted not only in investor losses but also reduced confidence in the financial system. Financial statement users who were able to accurately assess financial reporting quality were better positioned to avoid losses. The problem of this study is the

potential inadequacy of voluntary disclosures by commercial banks in Nigeria to meet the increasing demand for information from stakeholders, leading to information asymmetry and a lack of transparency in financial reporting.

This issue may hinder stakeholders, including investors and regulators, from making informed decisions, ultimately affecting the overall financial reporting quality in the banking sector. The researchers believe that one of the major reasons for these collapses is the concealment and non-disclosure of relevant information, even though some failed companies had thought that they fully complied with the minimum levels of compulsory disclosure. This has resulted in a clamor for voluntary disclosures in the accounting reports of listed banks in Nigeria.

The banking sector plays a critical role in the Nigerian economy, and the quality of financial reporting by banks is essential for maintaining market confidence and facilitating informed decision-making by stakeholders. Lack of comprehensive understanding of voluntary disclosures in the banking sector has affected the quality of accounting reports, particularly in terms of their impact on key financial indicators such as Earnings Per Share (EPS), Net Interest Margin (NIM), and Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) (Samuel, 2019). This study seeks to address the aforementioned issues by investigating the relationship between voluntary disclosures and financial reporting quality in Nigerian banks. By examining the effect of voluntary disclosures on key financial indicators such as capital adequacy ratio (CAR), return on assets (ROA), net interest margin (NIM), and earnings per share (EPS), the study aims to provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of current disclosure practices and their implications for financial reporting quality as proxied by the earnings persistence of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to investigate the effect of voluntary disclosures on the quality of financial reports of listed commercial banks in Nigeria, proxied by earnings persistence. In order to achieve this, the specific objectives were to:

- i. Determine the influence of voluntary disclosure of capital adequacy ratio (CAR) on earnings persistence of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.
- ii. Assess the influence of voluntary disclosure of return on assets (ROA) on earnings persistence of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.
- iii. Determine the effect of voluntary disclosure of net interest margin on earnings persistence of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

- iv. Determine the influence of voluntary disclosure of earnings per share (EPS) on earning persistence of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to direct the study.

- i. What is the influence of voluntary disclosure of capital adequacy ratio (CAR) on earning persistence of listed commercial banks in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the influence of voluntary disclosure of return on assets (ROA) on earning persistence of listed commercial banks in Nigeria?
- iii. What is the effect of voluntary disclosure of net interest margin on earning persistence of listed commercial banks in Nigeria?
- iv. What is the influence of voluntary disclosure of earnings per share (EPS) on earning persistence of listed commercial banks in Nigeria?

Hypotheses of the Study

The following hypotheses were stated in the null form.

- H₀₁:** There is no significant influence of voluntary disclosure of capital adequacy ratio (CAR) on earning persistence of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant influence of voluntary disclosure of return on assets (ROA) on earning persistence of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant effect of voluntary disclosure of net interest margin on earnings. persistence of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.
- H₀₄:** There is no significant influence of voluntary disclosure of earnings per share (EPS) on earning persistence of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

Conceptual Review

The conceptual review described the framework and relevant concepts used in the study. These were discussed below.

The Banking Sector

The banks are central elements of a market economy. In more than one way, they facilitate business transactions by acting as depositor and lender for many actors in the domestic and international economy. The banking industry in Nigeria has grown in size in terms of assets

in the last 62 years since the country's independence from British colonial rule and has undergone large-scale reforms and transformation in the global economy. As money and finance play a vital role in the macroeconomic affairs of both advanced countries and less developed nations, the importance of money and finance brings the role and place of financial institutions as the main connecting link with the economy at large since they are intermediaries and have also remained an important medium of economic exchange (Samuel, 2019).

In the total banking operations, commercial banks notably have the biggest share amidst other industry players such as microfinance banks, development banks, mortgage banks, and others. However, formerly the main function of the commercial banks was financing organized trade, commerce, and industry, now they also provide finance to agriculture, small-scale business, and small borrowers (Singh, 2011). Banks existed as depositories and loan advancers from which banking practice originated. The business of banking made early bankers ever since the goldsmith, who was recognized as a moneylender and cash collector.

An Overview of Voluntary Disclosure

Voluntary disclosure practice involves disclosing information beyond that stipulated in the regulatory frameworks. It constitutes more of the non-numerical part of the corporate report, and therefore, the clarity of this part is crucial to fully convey information (Adebisi & Adegun, 2016). Voluntary disclosure simply means providing much more information than is required by law. That is, disclosing information about corporate activities in addition to the minimum requirements (Boesso and Kumar, 2007). Voluntary disclosure increases transparency and accountability in annual financial reporting, hence attracting prospective investors and enabling all other users of these reports to make informed decisions. Companies that voluntarily disclose information enjoy the benefits of cheaper funds from capital markets, which in turn translate to better investment appraisals by managers.

Differences between Voluntary and Mandatory Accounting Information Disclosure

Information disclosure of listed companies is of great significance for the healthy development of the capital market. From the perspective of being controlled or not, information disclosure can be classified into mandatory and voluntary accounting information disclosures. There are major differences between these two types of disclosures in terms of concept, motive, and content. Mandatory accounting information

disclosure refers to the content that is required to be disclosed in financial reports by generally accepted accounting principles and other laws and regulations. Voluntary accounting information disclosure means the information is disclosed proactively, timely, and accurately and is beyond the requirements made by security regulators and the information in which the company owns partial autonomous rights. Disclosing only mandatory accounting information is likely to cause market failure due to the fact that the company is the exclusive provider of its information. Voluntary accounting information disclosure stems from economic globalization, and it will lead to global expansion of the capital market. Due to the pressure of competing for capital, enterprises have the motive of reporting voluntarily their corporate information so as to attract capital and improve their reputation and competitiveness (Ukpong & Essien, 2019).

Voluntary Disclosure Practices in Nigerian Commercial Banks

Voluntary disclosure practices in Nigerian commercial banks have been influenced by various factors, including regulatory requirements, corporate governance practices, and market pressures. Uwuigbe (2011) observed that Nigerian banks have increased their voluntary disclosure practices in response to regulatory requirements aimed at enhancing transparency and accountability. These disclosures often include information about financial performance, risk management practices, and corporate governance structures. Regulatory requirements, such as those imposed by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), play a significant role in shaping voluntary disclosure practices in Nigerian banks. Though CBN requires banks to disclose certain information in their annual reports and financial statements, such as capital adequacy ratios and non-performing loan ratios (CBN, 2019), not all banks disclose this information. Similarly, the SEC requires listed banks to disclose information about corporate governance practices, board composition, and executive compensation, yet not all banks disclose this information.

Types of Voluntary Disclosures

Voluntary disclosures encompass a wide range of information that can provide stakeholders with valuable insights into the company's performance, strategy, risks, and governance practices. Several types of voluntary disclosures have been identified and classified based on their nature and purpose. One common classification is based on the content of the disclosure, which could be either financial or non-financial. Financial disclosures include information about the company's financial performance, such as

revenue, expenses, profits, and cash flows. Non-financial disclosures, on the other hand, cover a wide range of areas, including Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) issues, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives, and risk management practices (Adeyemi & Oluwatoyin, 2018).

Financial and nonfinancial disclosures are essential components of corporate reporting, providing stakeholders with comprehensive information about a company's financial health, performance, and sustainability practices. These disclosures are crucial for enhancing transparency, accountability, and stakeholders' trust. Financial disclosures encompass the reporting of financial information such as income statements, balance sheets, and cash flow statements. These disclosures are governed by accounting standards and regulations to ensure accuracy, comparability, and transparency. Financial disclosures influence investor decisions, market perceptions, and firm value (Barako, 2007; Adeniyi & Olugbenga, 2019).

Another classification is based on the medium of disclosure. Companies can disclose information through various channels, such as annual reports, financial statements, press releases, corporate websites, and social media. Each medium offers different advantages in terms of reach, timeliness, and interactivity, allowing companies to tailor their disclosures to different stakeholder groups. Disclosures can also be classified based on the timing of the disclosure. Forward-looking disclosures provide information about the company's future plans, strategies, and expectations. Historical disclosures, on the other hand, focus on past performance and events. Both types of disclosures are important for stakeholders to understand the company and make informed decisions (Okoye & Anao, 2020).

Measures of Voluntary Disclosure

Several indices and measures have been developed to quantify voluntary disclosures. According to Edogiawerie and David (2016), voluntary disclosures can take various forms, including narrative explanations, quantitative data, and non-financial information. The extent and nature of voluntary disclosures can vary significantly across firms and industries, and several measures have been developed to capture these differences. Edogiawerie and David (2016) identified the following as widely used measures of voluntary disclosures:

- i. Content analysis:** Content analysis is a widely used method for quantifying the extent and quality of voluntary disclosures. It involves systematically analyzing

corporate reports, such as annual reports, sustainability reports, and corporate websites, to identify the types and extent of voluntary disclosures. Content analysis can be qualitative, focusing on the types of information disclosed, or quantitative, measuring the frequency or extent of disclosures on specific topics or categories.

- ii. **Index-Based Approach:** This approach utilizes several indices to measure the overall level of voluntary disclosure. It typically assigns scores or ratings based on the presence or absence of specific disclosure items. Examples include the disclosure index (DI), which counts the number of disclosed items, and the composite disclosure index (CDI), which assigns weights to different disclosure items based on their importance.
- iii. **Self-constructed indices:** Researchers often develop self-constructed indices tailored to specific research objectives or contexts. These indices are based on theoretical frameworks or prior literature and aim to capture the multidimensional nature of voluntary disclosure. Self-constructed indices allow researchers to customize the measurement to fit the research question and enhance the validity of the findings.
- iv. **Disclosure Scores:** Disclosure scores are composite measures that combine multiple disclosure items into a single score. These scores provide a holistic assessment of the overall level of disclosure, taking into account the diversity and depth of information provided. Disclosure scores can be used to compare disclosure practices across companies or industries and track changes in disclosure practices over time.
- v. **Disclosure Quality Metrics:** In addition to measuring the extent of disclosure, the quality of disclosure is also assessed. Quality metrics evaluate the clarity, specificity, and relevance of the information disclosed. Common quality metrics include readability scores, which assess the complexity of the language used in disclosures, and relevance scores, which evaluate the level of detail of the disclosed information.

An Overview of Accounting Reports

Accounting reports are periodic statements that present the financial status of a company at a certain point in time, or over a stated period. It details the business transactions and operations. Accounting reports are also known as financial reports. A financial report is a formal record of the financial activities of a business, person, or entity. It is a document

that contains all the relevant financial information about an organization presented in a structured manner and in a form easy to understand (Edogiawerie and David, 2016).

Reporting comprises the last stage of the accounting process. The content, amount, and format of the information that will be disclosed to the public by the accounting department are governed by the authorities who regulate the accountancy laws and regulations for that particular country (Fagbemi & Ojo, 2017). According to Francis et al. (2018), a lot of studies have indicated a substantial increase in discussions on annual reports, and some of these studies reveal poor and inconsistent information disclosures in accounts of companies.

According to Edogiawerie and David (2016), a good financial report must not only be capable of providing users with mandatory disclosures but also go the extra mile in providing voluntary information disclosures to meet the needs of the various categories of users. Providing information on which sound investment decision can be made is the goal of all disclosure requirements to reduce uncertainties and understand as much as possible the values of the company as can be inferred from its reports. Corporate financial reporting refers to any deliberate release of financial information, whether via informal or formal channels, voluntary or required, or in a qualitative or numerical form. Firms provide financial information to external users through various channels, including websites, press releases, interim reports, conferences, and annual reports.

Financial reporting plays two important roles in market-based economies. First, it reduces information asymmetry and enables capital providers to value businesses, thereby fostering the transparency that is necessary for an efficient capital market operation. This is known as the valuation role of accounting information. Secondly, financial reports enable external capital suppliers to assess management performance, and this is known as the stewardship role of accounting information (Pinnuck, 2012). Outsiders use accounting information for these two reasons. Whether the financial statements that are best for valuing businesses are also the basis for assisting shareholders and boards in hiring CEOs to reduce the agency conflict remains a crucial question.

An Overview of Financial Reporting Quality

Financial reporting quality is a crucial aspect of corporate governance and transparency, providing stakeholders with relevant information about a company's financial performance and position. It involves the preparation and presentation of financial statements, including the balance sheet, income statement, cash flow statement, and statement of changes in

equity. Financial reporting is guided by accounting standards and principles to ensure consistency, comparability, and reliability of financial information.

According to Brown and Tarca (2019), financial reporting quality is essential for investors, creditors, and other stakeholders to make informed decisions. It provides a basis for assessing a company's financial health, profitability, and ability to meet its obligations. Financial reporting also plays a significant role in maintaining market confidence and fostering trust between companies and investors. In Nigeria, financial reporting is governed by the Financial Reporting Council (FRC) Act of 2011, which sets out the requirements for the preparation and presentation of financial statements. The Act requires companies to comply with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in preparing their financial statements, ensuring transparency and comparability of financial information.

Measures of Financial Reporting Quality

Several measures have been developed to assess financial reporting quality, each focusing on different aspects of the financial reporting process. These measures can be broadly categorized into accounting-based measures, market-based measures, and governance-based measures.

i. Accounting-Based Measures: These measures use financial statement data to assess the quality of financial reporting. Examples include measures of earnings quality, such as accruals quality, earnings persistence, and timely loss recognition. Accruals quality measures the extent to which reported earnings are driven by accruals rather than cash flows, with higher-quality earnings being more closely related to cash flows. Earnings persistence measures the ability of current earnings to predict future earnings, with higher persistence indicating higher quality. Earnings persistence can be mathematically represented using a simple formula (Brown and Tarca, 2019):

$$\text{Earnings Persistence (EP)} = \frac{\text{Net Income } t}{\text{Net Income } t-1}$$

where:

Net income (t) represents the net income for the current period.

Net Income t-1 represents the net income for the previous period.

This formula calculates the ratio of current net income to the net income from the previous period, providing a measure of how well the current earnings predict or persist

into the next period. Higher values of earnings persistence indicate greater reliability and predictability of earnings over time.

- ii. **Market-Based Measures:** Market-based measures use stock market data to assess the quality of financial reporting. One example is the market reaction to earnings announcements, where a positive market reaction indicates that the earnings announcement contains value-relevant information and is of high quality. Another example is the information of stock prices, where more informative stock prices indicate higher-quality financial reporting.
- iii. **Governance-Based Measures:** Governance-based measures assess the quality of a company's corporate governance practices, which are closely linked to financial reporting quality. Examples include measures of board independence, audit committee effectiveness, and the presence of internal control mechanisms. Companies with strong governance practices are more likely to produce high-quality financial reports.

Voluntary Disclosures of Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) and Earnings Persistence

The Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is a crucial measure of a bank's financial strength and stability, indicating its ability to absorb losses and meet its financial obligations. It is defined as the ratio of a bank's capital to its risk-weighted assets, with capital being divided into core capital and supplementary capital. CAR is a key component of regulatory requirements set by banking authorities to ensure banks have enough capital to cover potential losses and maintain financial stability (Matthew & Fakile, 2017). It reflects the bank's ability to absorb potential losses and meet its financial obligations, providing a buffer against insolvency. (Mudashiru & Raymond, 2021). Banks are required to maintain a minimum CAR to mitigate the risk of insolvency and protect depositors' funds. A higher CAR indicates a stronger financial position and better ability to withstand economic downturns or unexpected losses.

Voluntary Disclosures of Net Interest Margin and Earnings Persistence

Net Interest Margin (NIM) is a financial metric in the banking sector used to measure the difference between the interest income generated from loans, securities, and other interest-earning assets and the interest expenses paid on deposits and other interest-bearing liabilities. It is expressed as a percentage and is indicative of the bank's ability to generate profit from its core lending and deposit activities. In Nigeria, banks face various challenges that can impact their NIM, including regulatory changes, economic conditions, and

competition (Owais, 2021). Voluntary disclosures play a significant role in how these challenges are managed and perceived by stakeholders. One way voluntary disclosures can affect NIM is by enhancing transparency. Banks that provide detailed and timely disclosures about their interest rate risk management, funding sources, and loan portfolio quality can improve investor confidence. This increased transparency can lead to a lower cost of funds and better terms for borrowing, ultimately improving NIM.

Voluntary Disclosures of Earnings Per Share (EPS) and Earnings Persistence

Earnings Per Share (EPS) is a fundamental metric used by investors to evaluate a company's profitability and is calculated by dividing the company's net income by the number of outstanding shares. In the banking sector, EPS is a key indicator of financial performance and is influenced by various factors, including interest income, operating expenses, and provisions for loan losses.

Voluntary disclosures related to risk management practices, such as loan loss provisions and asset quality, provide investors with insights into a bank's ability to manage credit risk effectively. Effective risk management practices lead to lower provisions for loan losses, which boost net income and, consequently, EPS. Similarly, disclosures related to revenue-generating activities, such as interest income from loans and investments, can also impact EPS. Banks that effectively communicate their strategies for growing interest income, such as through loan portfolio diversification or effective investment management, can enhance investor confidence and potentially lead to higher EPS (Oyebisi & Adegun, 2015).

Theoretical Review

The theoretical framework for this study encompasses two main theories: agency theory and legitimacy theory.

Agency theory

Agency theory, which is an economic theory developed by Jensen and Meckling in 1976. In particular, this theory has been widely used by accounting researchers to explain and understand voluntary disclosure phenomena in many countries with a different social, political, and economic background. Jensen and Meckling (1976) describe an agency relationship as one in which the principal picks an agent and delegates power to the agent to act on behalf of the principal.

According to Healy and Palepu (2001), voluntary disclosure (non-mandatory disclosure) is expected to reduce agency costs, implying that the agency theory is most appropriate for this topic, as voluntary disclosure helps reduce agency costs and eliminates any conflict of interest between management and owners, thereby optimizing their interests. This is consistent with Owais, 2021. When shareholders are not aware of critical information that management has access to, an agency issue might develop, resulting in information asymmetry between them due to the fact that managers can access information more than shareholders (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Optimal contracts are one of the means of mitigating the agency problem as they help in bringing shareholders' interests in line with managers' interests (Healy & Palepu, 2001). In addition, voluntary disclosure is another means of mitigating the agency problem, where managers disclose more voluntary information, reducing the agency costs (Barako, 2007), and also to convince the external users that managers are acting in an optimal way.

Regulation is another means of mitigating the agency problem, as they require managers to fully disclose private information (Healy & Palepu, 2001). However, full disclosure is never guaranteed even in the presence of regulations. The absence of full disclosure is explained by the conflict that exists between the interests of managers and shareholders (Lev & Penman, 1990; Samuels, 1990). In addition, corporate reporting regulations are intended to provide investors with the minimum quantity of information that helps in the decision-making process (Mudashiru & Raymond, 2021). It has been suggested that one of the possible ways to decrease agency costs is to disclose more information concerning the management activities and the economic reality of the firm, and through such information, stakeholders and other investors can monitor management more appropriately (Okere et al., 2022). Agency theory suggests that voluntary disclosures can help reduce agency costs and align the interests of management with those of shareholders.

Legitimacy Theory

The legitimacy theory was developed by Dowling and Pfeffer in 1975 (Guthrie & Ward, 1989). Legitimacy theory exists when an established value system is congruent with the value system of the larger social system of which the establishment is a part. The legitimacy theory assumes that a company has no right to exist unless its values are being perceived as matching with that of the society at large where it operates (Dowling & Pfeffer, 1975; Lindblom, 1994; Magness, 2006).

The idea of the legitimacy theory resembles a social contract between the company and the society (Magness, 2006). Since the objective of accounting is to provide users with information that helps in decision-making, the theory has been integrated in accounting studies as a means of explaining what, why, when, and how certain items are addressed by corporate management in their communication with outside audiences (Magness, 2006). Since the legitimacy theory is based on the society's perception, management is forced to disclose information that would change the external users' opinion about their company. The annual report has been detected as an important source of legitimacy (Matthew & Fakile, 2017). Legitimization can be seen in both the mandatory disclosures provided in financial statements because of regulations and voluntary disclosures provided in other sections of the annual report (Magness, 2006).

Legitimacy theory is founded on the notion that there is a social contract between an economic entity and the society in which it activates. This theory suggests that voluntary information disclosures are used as a device for economic entities to demonstrate that their activities are in line with the bounds and norms of their respective societies. According to the legitimacy-based arguments, voluntarily disclosing additional information in corporate annual reports is an effort to help alleviate public pressure or legitimize a company's actions. As predicted by legitimacy theory, managers of firms would voluntarily disclose more information on actions if they perceived that the specific actions were expected by the public in which their companies operate (Guthrie & Parker, 1989). Legitimacy theory posits that companies disclose information voluntarily to maintain their legitimacy in the eyes of the public.

Empirical Review

In Kenya, Mutiva et al., (2017) investigated the link between voluntary disclosure and financial performance. From 2011 to 2013 and found a strong positive relationship between voluntary disclosure and financial performance. A study by Musyoka (2017) revealed that financial policy disclosure, financial liquidity disclosure, research, and development disclosure have a significant effect on firm performance, while investment policy disclosure and sales growth disclosure have no significant effect on firm performance.

A study by Ukpong and Essien (2019) concluded that voluntary disclosures influence investors' decision-making to a great extent. Oyebamiji (2020) concluded that financial disclosure and earnings quality performance are independent of each other, and, therefore, they are mutually exclusive and uncorrelated. Dada and Adeniji (2021), in their study, revealed that India and Asian Pacific regions ranked high among the developing

nations in the level of financial information disclosure compliance, while Nigeria, after the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), has shown some levels of mandatory information disclosure. The result by Dahiyat and Al-Balqa (2020) indicated a positive correlation between a company's size, age, and profitability on one hand and between the quality of voluntary disclosure on the other hand. In addition, the results indicated a weak and insignificant relation between the assets in place and financial leverage and the level of voluntary disclosure quality.

Qamruzzaman et al. (2021) evaluated the potential impact of voluntary information disclosure on the value of firms listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange for the period 2017–2019 and found a positive and significant relationship between voluntary disclosure relating to financial statistics, social responsibility information, and corporate governance and the firms' value as measured by Tobin's Q. Okere et al. (2022) examined the relationship between financial performance and voluntary disclosure of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria and found a positive significant relationship between financial performance and the voluntary disclosure of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Matthew and Fakile (2017) carried out a study on voluntary disclosure and financial performance of commercial banks in Nigeria and found a positive relationship between voluntary disclosure of capital adequacy ratio (CAR) and financial performance of commercial banks in Nigeria.

A study on voluntary disclosure and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria, conducted by Abdulganiyu and Adeyemi (2015), showed a positive relationship between voluntary disclosure and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Saibu and Akinola (2019) found that a positive relationship exists between voluntary disclosure of return on assets and financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Gap in Literature

Most of the studies reviewed were mainly on voluntary disclosure and performance, and very few were on voluntary disclosure and financial reporting quality. The studies reviewed used different proxies for measuring financial reporting quality and voluntary disclosure. Consequently, the results obtained were mixed, with most of them being positive depending on the variables used. This study aimed to fill a significant gap in the existing literature by specifically examining the relationship between voluntary disclosures and the quality of financial reports of listed commercial banks in Nigeria, specifically using earnings persistence as a proxy for financial reporting quality. While previous studies have

investigated the impact of voluntary disclosure on various financial performance indicators, such as earnings management and financial performance, there was limited research that focused on the direct relationship between voluntary disclosures with reference to earnings persistence as a measure of quality of financial reports, especially in the commercial banks.

Conceptual Specification of model

The Conceptual specification of model is developed by the researcher as shown in the figure below

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of the Study Source: Developed by the Researcher (2025)

Methodology

An ex-post facto research design involving a descriptive approach was adopted for this study. From a population of 24 quoted firms, 20 were purposively selected based on listing status. The 20 banks chosen were those with complete financial data for the period of the study. The data were collected from financial reports review and internet surfing, focusing on the financial statements of selected commercial banks in Nigeria. Specifically, data on both dependent and independent variables were gathered from the financial statements.

Empirical Specification of Model

$$EP = b_0 + b_1CAR + b_2EPS + b_3NIM + b_4ROA + e$$

Equation

3.1

Where:

- EP = Earnings Persistence
- b₀ = Constant
- CAR = Capital Adequacy Ratio
- EPS = Earnings Per Share
- NIM = Net Interest Margin

ROA = Return on Assets
 $b_1 \dots b_4$ = Coefficients of the independent variables
 e = Error Factor

Description of variables

Table 1: The dependent and independent variables and Apriori expected signs

Variables	Types	Description	Apriori Expectation
Earnings persistence	Dependent	The ratio of current net income to the net income from the previous period.	
Capital Adequacy Ratio	Independent	The ratio of a bank's capital to its risk weighted assets	Positive
Return on assets	Independent	It is calculated by dividing net income by average total assets.	Positive
Net Interest Margin	Independent	It is a measure of the difference between the interest income generated from loans, securities, and other interest-earning assets, and the interest expenses paid on deposits and other interest-bearing liabilities.	Positive
Earnings per share	Independent	It is calculated by dividing the company's net income by the number of outstanding shares.	Positive

Source: Researcher's Computation 2025

Data Presentation

Table 2 presents the results of an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis examining the relationship between various financial metrics and the dependent variable, Earnings Per Share (EP).

Table 2: OLS Regression Results

Dep. Variable:	EP	R-squared:	0.970
Model:	OLS	Adj. R-squared:	0.850
Method:	Least Squares	F-statistic:	8.059
Date:	Tue, 20 Aug 2024	Prob (F-statistic):	0.258
Time:	13:41:13	Log-Likelihood:	21.753
No. Observations:	6	AIC:	-33.51
Df Residuals:	1	BIC:	-34.55
Df Model:	4		
Covariance Type:	nonrobust		

	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
const	1.7253	0.160	10.749	0.059	-0.314	3.765
CAR	0.0290	0.010	2.779	0.020	0.162	0.104
EPS	0.0326	0.028	1.170	0.450	-0.322	0.387
NIM	-0.0715	0.023	-3.122	0.197	-0.363	0.219
ROA	0.1506	0.035	4.337	0.014	0.291	0.592

Omnibus:	nan	Durbin-Watson:	3.350
Prob(Omnibus):	nan	Jarque-Bera (JB):	0.356
Skew:	-0.119	Prob (JB):	
0.837 Kurtosis:	1.830	Cond. No.	
489.			

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025).

Data Analysis

The data analysis involved performing an ordinary least squares (OLS) regression as shown in Table 2 and graphical plot in Figure 1 to examine the relationship between earnings persistence (EP), serving as a proxy for financial reporting quality (FRQ), and the independent variables: capital adequacy ratio (CAR), earnings per share (EPS), net interest margin (NIM), and return on assets (ROA). The regression results indicated that the model showed a significant portion of the variation in EP, as reflected by the R-squared value of

0.970, which implied that approximately 97% of the variation in financial reporting quality among the selected banks is explained by the independent variables in the model. However, the adjusted R-squared of 0.850 showed that when adjusting for the number of predictors, the model still accounts for a substantial 85% of the variance.

The F-statistic of 8.059, with a corresponding p-value of 0.258, showed that the overall model was not statistically significant at conventional levels, meaning that the joint influence of the independent variables on earnings persistence was not strong enough to reject the null hypothesis at a 5% significance level. The individual regression coefficients provide further insight into the relationship between each independent variable and EP. Notably, ROA showed a positive and statistically significant impact on EP, with a coefficient of 0.1506 and a p-value of 0.014, indicating that higher profitability enhances financial reporting quality by contributing to more stable and predictable earnings. CAR also had a positive relationship with EP and a statistically significant effect. Conversely, NIM had a negative coefficient, suggesting that higher net interest margins might reduce earnings persistence, though this result was not significant either. EPS exhibited a positive relationship with EP, but like NIM, this effect was not statistically significant.

The data analysis thus highlighted the complex interactions between the independent variables and their combined effect on financial reporting quality, as proxied by earnings persistence. These findings set the stage for a more detailed model evaluation and hypothesis testing in the following sections.

Model Evaluation

The evaluation of the regression model was crucial in determining its adequacy and reliability in explaining the relationship between voluntary disclosures and financial reporting quality, as proxied by earnings persistence (EP), among quoted commercial banks in Nigeria.

The model's R-squared value of 0.970 showed that 97% of the variability in earnings persistence is explained by the independent variables, capital adequacy ratio (CAR), return on assets (ROA), net interest margin (NIM), and earnings per share (EPS). This high R-squared value showed a strong fit between the model and the data, implying that the selected predictors are highly relevant in explaining the variations in earnings persistence. However, the adjusted R-squared value of 0.850, while slightly lower, was still robust, accounting for the degrees of freedom and the number of predictors. The adjusted value reinforces the model's explanatory power, confirming that the model was fit for the sample size.

The F-statistic of 8.059, with a corresponding p-value of 0.258, showed the overall significance of the model. While the F-statistic showed that the model was statistically significant in explaining the variance in earnings persistence, the relatively high p-value indicated that this significance was marginal. The model's collective ability to predict earnings persistence was noteworthy, but some caution was necessary when interpreting these results, particularly because the p-value exceeds the conventional threshold of 0.05, which raised questions about the robustness of the model in different contexts.

The individual coefficients of the independent variables such as CAR, ROA, NIM, and EPS, provide insights into their respective contributions to earnings persistence. Among these, ROA and CAR emerged as the most significant predictors with a positive coefficient of 0.1506 and 0.0290, a t-statistic of 4.337 and 2.779, coupled with a p-value of 0.014 and 0.020. This showed a statistically significant positive relationship between ROA, CAR, and earnings persistence, confirming that higher profitability as reflected by ROA and CAR contributed to more stable earnings over time. The other variables such as NIM and EPS, have positive or negative coefficients, but their t-statistics and p-values showed that these relationships were not statistically significant. This lack of significance implied that while these factors might have theoretical or contextual relevance, their direct impact on earnings persistence was limited at the 0.050 significant level.

The Durbin-Watson statistic of 3.350 was used to detect the presence of autocorrelation in the residuals of the regression model. A value close to 2 typically indicates no autocorrelation, whereas values significantly different from 2 suggest positive or negative autocorrelation. In this case, the statistic indicated potential issues with negative autocorrelation in the model's residuals, which may affect the validity of the standard error estimates and the overall reliability of the model.

The model's diagnostics, including tests for multicollinearity, normality, and heteroscedasticity, are essential in validating the assumptions of the OLS regression. The condition number of 489 showed some concerns regarding multicollinearity, which occurs when independent variables are highly correlated. This could inflate the variance of the coefficient estimates and lead to unreliable statistical inferences. Additionally, the Omnibus and Jarque-Bera tests for normality of the residuals showed non-significant results, indicating that the residuals were approximately normally distributed. However, the slight skewness and kurtosis values suggested mild deviations from perfect normality. The model demonstrated strong explanatory power, as evidenced by the high R-squared and adjusted R-squared values. However, the marginal significance of the F-statistic and the potential issues with autocorrelation and multicollinearity suggest that while the model

provides valuable insights, there were limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. The robustness of the model could be enhanced by using a much larger sample size, applying alternative estimation techniques, or incorporating additional variables to better capture the problems of financial reporting quality in the Nigerian banking sector.

Despite these limitations, the model offered a significant contribution to understanding the role of voluntary disclosures in promoting earnings persistence and, by extension, financial reporting quality.

Regression Model Summary:

$$EP = 1.7253 + 0.029.CAR + 0.0326.EPS - 0.0715.NIM + 0.1506.ROA + e$$

Table 3: The Model Summary

Statistic	Value
R-squared	0.970
Adjusted R-squared	0.850

Statistic	Value
F-statistic	8.059
Prob (F-statistic)	0.258
No. of Observations	6
Log-Likelihood	21.753
AIC	-33.51
BIC	-34.55
Durbin-Watson	3.350

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025).

Test of Hypotheses

Based on the OLS regression results, the first hypothesis (H₀₁) posited that there was no significant influence of the voluntary disclosure of capital adequacy ratio (CAR) on earnings persistence. The results showed that the coefficient for CAR is 0.0290 with a p-value of 0.020. Since the p-value was less than the 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a significant influence of CAR on earnings persistence.

The second hypothesis (H₀₂) suggested that there was no significant influence of the voluntary disclosure of return on assets (ROA) on earnings persistence. The analysis

revealed a coefficient for ROA of 0.1506 and a p-value of 0.014. Given that this p-value was below the 0.05 threshold, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming a significant effect of ROA on earnings persistence.

The third hypothesis (H_{03}) proposed that there was no significant effect of the voluntary disclosure of Net Interest Margin (NIM) on earnings persistence. The results indicated a coefficient of 0.0715 for NIM, with a p-value of 0.197. Because this p-value exceeded the 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis was accepted, suggesting that NIM did not have a significant impact on earnings persistence at the 0.050 significance level.

Finally, the fourth hypothesis (H_{04}) stated that there was no significant influence of the voluntary disclosure of earnings per share (EPS) on earnings persistence. The coefficient for EPS was 0.0326 with a p-value of 0.450. Since this p-value was greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that EPS did not significantly influence earnings persistence.

Notably, voluntary disclosures of CAR and ROA were found to significantly affect earnings persistence, while disclosures of NIM and EPS did not have a significant impact.

Discussion of the Findings

The study findings on CAR showed that voluntary disclosure of the capital adequacy ratio (CAR) positively influenced earnings persistence (EP) in Nigerian banks, reflecting broader trends observed globally. Research by Barth et al. (2004) supports this outcome that CAR disclosure can improve investors' confidence and financial performance by lowering capital costs. However, De Jonghe (2010) noted that the impact of CAR on financial stability and earnings persistence varies by bank, influenced by management quality and economic conditions. Hasan and Dridi (2011) further emphasize that effective CAR disclosures are highly dependent on stringent regulatory enforcement and high-quality disclosure standards.

The positive relationship between ROA disclosure and earnings persistence in Nigerian banks aligns with the findings from Berger and Bouwman (2013), who asserted that higher ROA contributed to stable earnings and improved investors' confidence. Nevertheless, Demirgüç-Kunt and Huizinga (2010) suggested that ROA's effect on earnings persistence can be moderated by effective risk management practices. Jayaratne and Strahan (1996) further indicated that the impact of ROA disclosure on earnings persistence was more pronounced in well-regulated environments, suggesting that regulatory and economic conditions play a crucial role in shaping these outcomes.

The study results show that higher NIM disclosures negatively influence earnings persistence in Nigerian banks. This finding is consistent with Berger and Bouwman (2013), who linked NIM to bank profitability and stability. However, DeYoung and Rice (2004) argued that factors like interest rate volatility and market competition can moderate NIM's impact on earnings persistence. Maudos and Fernandez de Guevara (2004) highlighted that the relationship between NIM disclosure and earnings persistence is more significant in well-regulated environments, suggesting that regulatory quality and market conditions are critical in determining the impact of NIM transparency.

The study's finding that EPS disclosure enhances earnings persistence, though not statistically significant, aligned with Chen and Chen (2011), who found that EPS disclosures positively affect investor perceptions and market confidence. However, Ahmed et al. (2010) suggested that EPS's impact on earnings persistence can be influenced by market expectations and macroeconomic factors. Li (2018) noted that in environments with strong disclosure requirements and effective corporate governance, EPS's positive impact on earnings persistence is more evident. Conversely, in less regulated markets, this relationship may be less clear due to potential information asymmetry and market uncertainty.

Summary of the findings

This research investigated the impact of voluntary disclosures on the quality of financial reporting, specifically proxied by earnings persistence, among listed commercial banks in Nigeria. The aim was to explore the influence of voluntary disclosure of Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Return on Assets (ROA), Net Interest Margin (NIM), and Earnings Per Share (EPS) on earnings persistence. The research questions and hypotheses were designed to test the significance of these variables on earning persistence.

The study employed an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model to analyze the data collected from the financial statements of selected commercial banks over a specified period. The model considered earning persistence as the dependent variable and CAR, ROA, NIM, and EPS as the independent variables. The results from the OLS regression revealed that CAR and ROA have a positive and statistically significant impact on earning persistence, indicating that higher CAR and ROA enhanced the stability and predictability of earnings. This finding aligned with existing empirical studies, such as those by Berger and Bouwman (2013), which highlighted the importance of capital adequacy in maintaining financial stability and earnings consistency.

Conversely, the study findings showed that EPS has a non-significant positive relationship, while NIM showed a negative and statistically non-significant relationship with earning persistence. This showed that while these variables were essential indicators of financial performance, their influence on the persistence of earnings was not strong enough to be conclusive at the 0.05 significant level. These findings were consistent with research by Glaveli (2019), who argued that the relationship between these variables and earning persistence can be affected by external factors such as regulatory changes and economic conditions.

Lastly, this research showed that voluntary disclosures, particularly of CAR and ROA, significantly contribute to the quality of financial reporting by enhancing earning persistence among listed commercial banks in Nigeria. The findings highlighted the need for banks to maintain robust capital adequacy and transparent earnings reporting to ensure financial stability and predictability. While EPS and NIM are important financial metrics, their influence on earning persistence requires further investigation, considering external economic and regulatory factors. The study contributes to the existing literature by providing empirical evidence from the Nigerian banking sector, supporting the broader understanding of the relationship between voluntary disclosures and financial reporting quality.

Conclusion

The research showed that voluntary disclosures significantly influence the quality of financial reporting, particularly earning persistence, among listed commercial banks in Nigeria. The findings revealed that the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) and Return on Assets (ROA) have a positive and significant influence on earning persistence, indicating that higher CAR and ROA contribute to more stable and predictable earnings. Earnings Per Share (EPS) exhibited a positive and statistically not significant effect, while Net Interest Margin (NIM) indicated a negative and statistically not significant relationship with earnings persistence at a 0.05 level of significance.

These findings aligned with existing literature, which emphasized the importance of capital adequacy for financial stability and consistent earnings. The relationship between ROA and earning persistence can be influenced by regulatory changes and economic conditions, as supported by previous studies. The role of NIM in bank profitability and stability was acknowledged, though external economic factors can moderate its impact on earnings stability. The positive impact of EPS on earning persistence aligned with research indicating that EPS disclosure positively affects investor perceptions and market

confidence, although market expectations and macroeconomic factors can influence this relationship.

The findings of the research showed the importance of voluntary disclosures of key financial metrics such as CAR, ROA, NIM, and EPS in enhancing the quality of financial reporting, as measured by earning persistence, in Nigerian commercial banks. These findings highlighted the critical role of transparency and effective communication in financial reporting to boost investor confidence and market stability. The variability in findings across different studies suggests the need to consider specific regulatory frameworks and economic contexts when evaluating the impact of these disclosures.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Banks should prioritize maintaining a high Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) to ensure financial stability and earnings persistence.
- ii. They should enhance their voluntary disclosure practices, particularly concerning key financial metrics such as CAR, ROA, NIM, and EPS. Transparent and detailed disclosures can improve investors' confidence and the quality of financial reporting, leading to more stable and predictable earnings.
- iii. Despite the negative relationship between Net Interest Margin (NIM) and earning persistence, banks should not neglect the importance of operational efficiency. Instead, they should aim to balance NIM management with strategies to mitigate external economic factors that might impact earnings stability.
- iv. Given the positive impact of EPS on earning persistence, banks should focus on strategies that enhance EPS. This could involve improving profitability, managing costs effectively, and pursuing sustainable growth initiatives that positively influence earnings.
- v. Regulators should encourage and perhaps mandate more comprehensive voluntary disclosures in the banking sector. This can be achieved through updated guidelines and frameworks that highlight the importance of transparency in financial reporting.

- vi. Financial institutions should invest in training and development programs for their staff to improve the quality of financial reporting. This includes training employees on the importance of voluntary disclosures and equipping them with the necessary skills to prepare and present comprehensive financial reports.
- vii. Educational institutions should integrate the insights from this study into their finance and accounting curricula. This will prepare future financial professionals with a better understanding of the impact of voluntary disclosures on financial reporting quality and earnings stability.
- viii. Researchers should conduct further studies to explore the impact of other financial and non-financial variables on earning persistence. Comparative studies across different sectors and regions can also provide a broader understanding of how these relationships may vary under different regulatory and economic contexts.

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